

Lexical Richness of L2 Production Using Nation and Laufer's Lexical Frequency Profile

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Abstract

The study assessed the essays' lexical richness in two hundred words each essay among the Second Year College Filipino and Nigerian students at St. Dominic College of Asia, Philippines in K1 words (1-1,000), K2 words (1,001-2,000), Academic Word List (AWL), and Off-List Words. Essay 1 - SOGIE Bill, and Essay 2, one (1) topic of students' choice: (2.a) Money; (2.b) Happiness; (2.c) knowledge-based economy. The descriptive- correlational design was used with frequency-percentage count and test of significant difference was computed to determine the lexical richness of the respondents' essays. The Research Ethics Committee approved the research protocol in an expedite manner, hence; a low-risk study. The findings of the study revealed that most of the words used by Filipino and Nigerian students fall under K1 words (1-1,000) level. The lexical richness for both Filipino and Nigerian College Students' Essays 1 and 2 showed the computed p-value of 0.000 lower than .05 alpha level. The difference is significant, hence; the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the word level for Essays 1 and 2 for both respondent-groups, and there is no significant difference in the percentage of words used among K2 words level (1,001-2,000), Academic Word List (AWL), and Off-List Words. However, the Filipino and Nigerian students used Off-List Words from K3 – K9 revealing the breadth of their vocabulary knowledge. Lexical frequency profile is a reliable measure on the lexical richness in L2 production. The English vocabulary of students has been enriched by their exposure and use of it in school and at home. The educational level of the parents, the availability of quality reading materials in English, and the socio-economic status of the family could be given consideration among other factors for future research undertakings.

Keywords: Lexical richness. Essay. L2 production. Filipinos. Nigerians.

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Introduction

Learning a language requires the acquisition of the listening, speaking, reading, and writing skills. Of the four skills, writing is the hardest to learn and develop because the learners should acquire sufficient vocabulary to be able to perform well in school and out. Even the English native speakers claimed that it will take many years to acquire a good writing skill. In a similar setup, non-native speakers of English may have experienced more difficulties than the native ones. The three other skills should establish a functional relationship with the richness of the vocabulary acquired through writing as an active and productive process. Olinghouse and Wilson (2013), as cited in Crossley and McNamara (2011), Staehr (2008), and Grobe (1981), argued that vocabulary growth is associated with the vocabulary used in reading and other skills. Moreover, the words that writers choose are important since the quality of a piece of writing is heavily influenced by the vocabulary used.

Laufer and Nation (1995), emphasized that the writer's vocabulary size is a major element of the vocabulary employed in written production, especially if the writer is a second language learner with a limited vocabulary compared to native speakers. Lexical richness measures seek to quantify the extent to which a writer use a diverse and broad vocabulary. This has sparked the interest in such measures for two reasons: they can be used to identify some of the aspects that influence the quality of a piece of writing, and they can be used to investigate the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and use. Alfadle (2016), in a study, supported the argument of Nation and Laufer when it was discovered using Multivariate analyses (n=95) which indicated that students gained an average of 800-1,000 words per year and vocabulary growth increased significantly throughout the study, indicating strong vocabulary increase by a huge effect over every year of study. Uchiyama and Clenton (2018), stipulated that the size of one's vocabulary was found to be highly related to one's vocabulary rating. However, during the speech, learners with large vocabulary sizes did not always develop lexically sophisticated L2 words. In a similar direction, Hajiyeva (2015), in a study on the relationship between receptive and productive vocabulary sizes and their increased use, claimed that productive vocabulary went up by 21 percent, but the students' overall receptive vocabulary knowledge was greater than their product knowledge, with the gap narrowing after a year. Despite receiving education for a year, students still do not have the necessary vocabulary to achieve their learning objectives.

The results relate to the reality that writing as a productive skill is not easy to learn, much more to master because learning and relearning it goes with time. Yunus et al., (2016) supported the prior statement because in their study they discovered that UniSZA students' superior average score was mostly attributed to their early exposure to formal English education in schools.

This study concluded that explicit academic vocabulary education should be provided to students, particularly in the first semester of an English program, in order to meet the academic and professional needs of English major students in the future. However, assessing the lexical richness of college students' two written essays and by comparing the results of the two-group, Filipino (geographically in Southeast Asia) and Nigerian (geographically in West Africa) college students, who are taking similar courses and of the same level, but different cultural orientation and background seem less unexplored. With the given background, the study was pursued to assess the percentage of lexical richness in Essays 1 & 2 of Filipino and Nigerian students in K1 words (1-1,000), K2 words (1,001-2,000), Academic Word List (AWL), Off-List Words, and the significant difference in the lexical richness in Essays 1 & 2 for both respondent-group.

Methodology

This study used descriptive-correlational design. Because it describes, explains, and verifies findings, descriptive research is the ideal method for describing facts and characteristics of what is being investigated. Following creative investigation, description organizes the discoveries in order to fit them with explanations, which are subsequently tested or validated. (Bickman and Rog, 1998). While correlational studies are generally used to determine whether two or more variables have a relationship (Kumar, 2011). In a purposive sampling, is a type of non-probability sampling in which researchers choose people of the population to participate in their study based on their own assessment (Alchemer, 2020). There were 50 respondents consisted of two groups: 25 Filipino College students and 25 Nigerian College students both have their mother tongue/native language and have gone to school with English as their second language. They wrote two essays in two hundred words each. Essay 1 – Are you in favor of the Sexual Orientation and Gender Identity Expression (SOGIE) Bill? and Essay 2, one (1) topic of students' choice in a list of three: (2.a) Money is not after all the be-all and end-all of happiness; (2.b) Happiness is a choice; (2.c) Citizens who are aware and skilled contribute to economic progress in a knowledge-based economy. Informed consent was sought from the respondents and ethical review was done by the Research Ethics Committee of St. Dominic College of Asia.

The presentation, interpretation, and analysis of data using frequency and percentage, test of significant difference, and ranking were utilized to derive an appropriate statistical and tabular presentation. The adopted theory is from Nation and Laufer's Lexical Frequency Profile with citation of related literature for the last five years and some studies dated a decade back were cited to establish the thread of research findings and the conversation among scholars in vocabulary. As shown in the contents, the citations closely relate to the findings of the study.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 Lexical Richness in Essay 1 for Filipino and Nigerian Respondents

Nationality	Level of Words	Percentage	Rank
Filipino	K1 words (1-1,000)	84.94	1
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	3.75	4
	Academic Word List (AWL)	4.95	3
	Off-List Words	6.35	2
TOTAL		100.00	
Nigerian	K1 words (1-1,000)	84.68	1
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	3.38	4
	Academic Word List (AWL)	6.08	2
	Off-List Words	5.85	3
TOTAL		100.00	

In Essay 1, most of the words used by the Filipino College students fall under K1 words (1-1,000) with 84.94 percent, rank 1; followed by the Off-List Words with 6.35 percent, rank 2; Academic Word List (AWL), 4.95 percent, rank 3; and K2 words (1,001-2,000) with 3.75 percent, rank 4. With the Nigerian College students, most of their words fall under K1 words (1-1,000) with a percentage of 84.69; followed by Academic Word List (AWL) with 6.08 percent; Off-List Words with 5.85 percent; and K2 words (1,001-2,000) with 3.38 percent.

The Off-List Words in the first essay of Filipino students cover 20 words: 13 in the K3 (2,001-3,000) such as: *approve, arise, biological, ban, congress, disagree, discriminate, destruction, dimensional, distinguish, fading, harsh, and innovation*; six in the K4 (3,001-4,000) – *acquaintance, aspire, certificate, disadvantage, deprive, and invade*; one in the K6 (5,001-6,000), *defection*. In the first essay of Nigerian students which covers 11 words, nine in the K3 (2,001-3,000) – *approve, Catholic, disagree, domination, decrease, fulfill, infection, investment, and negative*; one word in the K4 (3,001-4,000) – *literate*; and one word in the K9 (8,001-9,000) – *leak*. The use of words beyond the K1, K2, and AWL revealed the growing vocabulary of college students which may not be sophisticated for the moment, but it will expand as they continue their college studies and complete their degree in a couple of years from now. Laufer and Nation (1995) had shown that the LFP has a good correlation with other lexical measures, can distinguish between learners of different proficiency levels, and is relatively consistent between two pieces of writing by the same student. Moreover, Zhai (2016) claimed and demonstrated that the respondents relied more on the first 1,000-word level to describe their meanings, and lexical sophistication and variation are low. Subjects with varying writing abilities use varied language, but there are only substantial changes in lexical variation, not lexical sophistication, between the two groups.

Table 2 Lexical Richness in Essay 2 for Filipino and Nigerian Respondents

Nationality	Level of Words	Percentage	Rank
Filipino	K1 words (1-1,000)	91.87	1
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	2.89	2
	Academic Word List (AWL)	2.55	4
	Off-List Words	2.69	3
TOTAL		100.00	
Nigerian	K1 words (1-1,000)	92.99	1
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	2.31	3
	Academic Word List (AWL)	2.59	2
	Off-List Words	2.11	4
TOTAL		100.00	

The lexical richness in Essay 2 among the Filipino respondents reveals that most of the words used fall under K1 words (1-1,000) with 91.87 percent, rank 1; followed by K2 words (1,001- 2,000) with 2.89 percent, rank 2; Off-List Words with 2.69 percent, rank 3; Academic Word List (AWL) 2.55 percent, rank 4. However, nine words were identified with K3 (2,001-3,000): *legislator, marginalization, negative, offense, provision, solve, suicide, solution, and wealth*; in K4 (3,001-4,000) – *recreation, harassment, foremost, lesbian, and upgrading*; in K5 (4,001-5,000), *tolerance*; in K6 (5,001-6,000) – *intolerable and overtaking*; in K7 (6,001-7,000), *overpower*. For Nigerian respondents, most of their words fall under K1 words (1-1,000) with 92.99 percent, rank 1; followed by Academic Word List (AWL) with 2.59 percent, rank 2. Some of their words fall under K2 words (1,001-2,000) with 2.31 percent, rank 3; and other words fall under Off-List Words with 2.11 percent, rank 4; five words in K3 (2,001-3,000) – *permission, peer, religion, suicide, and succeed*; four words in K4 (3,001-4,000), *caution, guardian, preach, and worship*; one word in K5 (4,001-5,000) – *inferior*; one word in K6 (5001-6000) – *deceive*. The results of Essay 1 are very identical with Essay 2 revealing the level, breadth, or size of the college students' vocabulary within K1 (1 – 1000). Their vocabulary uptake revolves within that level relating to the reading habits of students since they learned to read their college textbooks or any reading materials in English form which have affected the level of vocabulary.

In a similar study (Li and Kirby, 2015), the researchers investigated the influences of two dimensions of vocabulary knowledge, namely, breadth of vocabulary (number of words known) and depth of vocabulary (richness of word knowledge), on different aspects of English reading in Chinese high school students studying English as a second language. The results revealed that vocabulary breadth and depth were modestly associated. They both helped people read words, but the breadth had a bigger impact than the depth of vocabulary. The four LFP data are inextricably linked and statistically difficult to deal with.

This is something that the authors are aware of, and to address it, Laufer and Nation (1995) proposed Beyond 2000, which is a simplified profile of the LFP. The percentage of word families in the text that are not in the first 2,000 is used to compute the Beyond 2000 score. As a result, the value of Beyond 2000 would be 10%. Laufer and Nation (1995) argued that Beyond 2000 is just as accurate and valid as the LFP, but it only permits one figure to be calculated rather than numerous, making it easier to compare lexical richness to other factors (such as passive vocabulary size).

Table 3 Significant Difference in Lexical Richness in Essay 1 between Filipino and Nigerian Students

Nationality	Level of Lexical Richness	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision	
Filipino	K1 words (1-1,000)	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
		Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
		Off-List Words	.000	Significant	Reject
Nigerian	K1 words (1-1,000)	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
		Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
		Off-List Words	.000	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The level of lexical richness for both Filipino and Nigerian College students in Essay 1 shows the computed p-value of 0.000 is lower than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference is significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the word level for Essay 1 of Filipino students.

In similar direction, the computed p-value of 0.000 is lower than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference is significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the word level for Essay 1 of Nigerian students.

Similar findings by Ibrahim et al., (2019) supported the present findings, which It also aims to see if there are any significant changes in the use of the 1,000-, 2,000-word levels, the AWL, and the words not-in-the-List/Off-List terms between the two essays of the respondent-groups. The preceding technique was carried out using the RANGE software developed by Heatley et al. (2002). This study has pedagogical implications for vocabulary instruction in the language classroom, with a particular focus on the development of lexical richness in EFL students' written work.

Table 4 Significant Difference in Lexical Richness in Essay 2 between Filipino and Nigerian Students

Nationality	Level of Lexical Richness	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
Filipino	K1 words (1-1,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
	Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
Nigerian	K1 words (1-1,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
	K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
	Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
	Off-List Words	.000	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The Post Hoc test was done to identify which of the word level is statistically significant for Essay 1. Both Filipino and Nigerian respondents' word-level shows that the percentage of K1 words (1-1,000) is statistically higher than the percentage of other word levels. It is shown that in Essay 1 most of the respondents used words within the K1 words (1-1,000). Moreover, the percentage of K2 words (1,001-2,000) is statistically higher than the percentage of words under Off- List Words.

This would mean that there are more words used and can be found in K2 (1,001-2,000) than Off-List Words. Several studies have discovered a relation between lexical diversity and language proficiency, suggesting that higher-rated essays had more lexical diversity (Crossley, et al., 2014, as cited in Crossley, et al., 2014; Jarvis, 2002; Engber, 1995; Linarud, 1986). Engber (1995) noted that lexical variance, including lexical errors ($r = .45$) and excluding errors ($r = .57$), and a holistic score of writing quality were found to have significant correlations. Essays using a broader vocabulary were given higher marks. Hence, lexical richness is seen through the essays of the participants. Using the Lexical Frequency Profile, Laufer and Nation (1995) showed that in their texts, more proficient L2 learners used significantly fewer high-frequency terms. Word frequency counts based on different corpora produced similar results in some research (Crossley & McNamara, 2011, as cited in Crossley, et al., 2014; Crossley, et al. 2014; Crossley, et al., 2013; McNamara, et al., 2010; Cumming et al., 2005; Read, 2000; Engber, 1995). Hence, as a person's language skill improves, so does their lexical sophistication. A recent study by Kyle and Crossley (2015) stated that the researchers looked at lexical sophistication in argumentative L2 writing and discovered a relationship between word range and essay quality (BNC Written Range All Words indicated 16.7% of the variance in essay scores). As a result, higher-rated essays are more likely to use words with a narrower word range that includes more particular and domain-appropriate terms. However, more study is needed to see if word range is a reliable predictor of essay quality across a variety of disciplines and language levels (Kyle & Crossley, 2015).

Table 5 Significant Difference in Lexical Richness in Essay 1

Level of Lexical Richness	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
K1 words (1-1,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
Off-List Words	.000	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The test for the significant difference in the level of lexical richness for both Filipino and Nigerian College students in Essay 1, of which the computed p-value is 0.000 is lower than .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference is significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the word level in Essay 1 for Filipino respondents.

Along that direction, the computed p-value is 0.000 is lower than the .05 alpha level. Hence, the difference is significant, and the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the word level in Essay 1 for Nigerian respondents. As Nation (2001) stipulated that vocabulary knowledge is diverse and therefore, there is no single index that can accurately indicate vocabulary competency or performance, or any other linguistic domain for that matter (Malvern & Richards, 1997). Attempting to characterize learners' vocabulary using a single measure of lexical richness is thus a simplification, and it will be essential to complement this with further analyses that can provide insights into qualitative features of vocabulary knowledge and use.

Table 6 Significant Difference in Lexical Richness in Essay 2

Level of Lexical Richness	p-value	Significance	Ho Decision
K1 words (1-1,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
K2 words (1,001-2,000)	.000	Significant	Reject
Academic Word List (AWL)	.000	Significant	Reject
Off-List Words	.000	Significant	Reject

*Significant at .05 alpha level

The Post Hoc test determined which of the word levels is statistically significant for Essay 2 both for Filipino and Nigerian respondents which reported that the percentage of K1 words (1-1,000) is statistically higher than the percentage of other word levels. The respondents' write up in Essay 2 used most of their words within the K1 words (1-1,000). Results further show that there is no significant difference in the percentage of words used in K2 words (1,001-2,000), Academic Word List (AWL), and Off-List Words. As expressed in the previous findings, the lexical richness of college students hovered within K1 words (1-1,000), which revealed their vocabulary level is more than enough to succeed in their academic life.

However, it is significant for learners to improve further, their proficiency in the use of English through the help of their English language teachers in the use of social English and academic English. Within a few months, the former may begin to manifest. However, English Language learners will most likely need a few years to properly develop social English skills in listening, speaking, reading, and writing. An improvement of their Social English is the prelude toward improving and acquiring skills in their Academic English. Colorin Colorado (n.d.) describes that Academic English is the language that is required for academic success. It is indeed integrated to a standards-based curriculum that includes Math, Science, Social Studies, and English language arts.

Conclusion and Recommendation

The English vocabulary level of college students is not only enriched by their exposure to the second language in school but by other intervening factors at home with the presence of parents who are using English vis-à-vis the mother/native tongue, their educational level, the availability of quality reading materials in English, and the socio-economic status of the family. The findings of the study are closely related to the dearth of some desirable factors which affect the learning and acquisition of vocabulary information, the depth and breadth of it. Hence, Filipino and Nigerian college students have sufficient K1 words level of vocabulary to succeed in their academic life along with the use of AWL and Off-List words in significant level. This contention is supported by Baker et al. (1998), that the strength of a student's vocabulary is a strong predictor of their performance. The reason for this is because anyone's understanding of a subject is founded on the vocabulary of that material (Marzano and Pickering, 2005). Finally, the Lexical Frequency Profile is a consistent indicator of lexical richness across two pieces of writing by the same students. However, a further study is encouraged to validate the present findings and or establish a new dimension in vocabulary learning and acquisition with a strong emphasis on the breadth and depth of acquired vocabulary.

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